

SEMANTIC COMPATIBILITY OF COMPOUND SENTENCES IN TRANSLATIONS

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Annotation: *Translation difficulties are not limited to linguistic differences. Sometimes the problem of translating from a new language is more complicated than from a long language. Although the languages to be translated or to be translated are lexically-grammatically and structurally distant from each other, the problem of translation is that if they feel similarity, commonality, harmony, commonality in terms of subject, literary tradition, stage of cultural development of two languages the possibility of a successful solution arises.*

Keywords: *compound sentence, translation, meaning, work, problem, style, repetition, lexical-grammatical.*

Schoolmates and stylists can create true works of art by translating each other's works. In the practice of literary translation, this is still considered a typical hoi.

Language is one of the most important indicators of a work of art. In translation, this main factor changes, one language is replaced by another, and as the language changes, there is sometimes a phenomenon of methodological shift. In many cases, the interpreter himself consciously allows this to happen, using it as a precaution.

"I hope she's not ill."

"Isn't he sick?"

"I think we can get you the silver."

"Anyway, we're going to try to be silver."

In this case, the phenomenon of stylization, that is, methodological adaptation, arises. The aim is to convince the reader that the work being translated is in the form of descriptions and descriptions of events, leaving no doubt in its naturalness, but such adaptations, which are used for surfing, instead of the naturalness of the image rhythm, create inconsistencies.

In translation, it is a mistake to think that the formal features of a work are insignificant, even if they can be ignored. In a correct translation, it is not the

formal logical-grammatical indicators of the original, the categorical features of the phrases, the indicators of type, color, inclination, gender, but the idea expressed by them that leads. This is because certain word groups or parts of speech can be represented by completely different grammatical elements and categories.

"After I was wounded I never found him"

"Soon I forgot about him."

"We are brothers and we love each other"

"You and I are brothers, we love each other."

"I wish you were back."

"Get well soon and rub"

"You'll fight before you'll marry?"

"Either you fight or you die."

"I felt him in his metal box against my chest while we drove."

"As I was sitting in the car, his metal sheath was sticking to my chest."

In the original, whether it is a compound sentence or a compound sentence, a simple sentence or a compound sentence, a sentence, a question or an exhortation - all of these, that is, the grammatical form as a whole, are closely related to the content or thought expressed. will depend. Whether the sentence structure is given with a grammatically appropriate content that is significantly more relevant to the original, or whether its syntactic device is broken and fragmented, depends on how accurately the original style is reflected. . It should never be confused with formality.

In the 19th century, a Russian translator of Dickens's works often omitted repetitions of the author's work. KI Chukovsky argues that "such repetitions are very important for the writer's style, and not to give them in translation is tantamount to betraying the Dickens style."

According to A.V. Fedorov, " translators often face the problem of reflecting the rhythm of translation in the translation of prose works. However, this feature, reflected in the work of each writer, is based on the lexical-phonetic, grammatical-structural means of the language, which in the process of translation is blindly

It's not safe to move. In translation, each writer's style must be re-created, taking into account the capabilities and characteristics of the other language."

In the translation of "Goodbye Weapon" I. Gafurov gave very good examples of expressing the meaning of the sentence structure without interfering with the meaning.

“ The summer went that way. I do not remember much about the days, except that they were hot and that there were many victories in the papers. I was very healthy and my legs healed quickly so that it was not very long after I was first on crutches before I was through with them and walking with a cane. Then I started treatments at the Ospedale Maggiore for bending the knees, mechanical treatments, baking in the box of mirrors with violet rays, massage and baths. I went over there afternoons, and afterward stopped at the cafe and had a drink and read the papers. I did not roam around the town; but wanted to get home to the hospital from the cafe. AH I wanted to see Catherine”

It simply came to our notice then. I don't remember many of them, but I remember that it was hot in the air and the newspapers were full of news of victory. My hair was very healthy and my wounds started to heal quickly. I didn't need to walk two or three times with my armpits, and I started walking with a cane. That's when I joined Ospedale Maggiore and started practicing knee flexion. I started doing movement therapy, putting my feet in purple rays in a mirror box, massaging, taking a bath, and so on. I would go there in the afternoon, and on my way back I would go to the cafe, drink wine, and read the newspaper. I didn't want to go around the city, I just wanted to go straight from the cafe to the hospital. I just wanted to see Catherine.

The seven-sentence original in English is a masterpiece translated into Uzbek with nine sentences. The issue is not the quantity of words, but the unity of thought, the depth of content, the natural sound. However, when translating a work of art from one language to another, it must come from the content, not from the grammatical structure of the sentences, or from the number of sentences in it, without giving up the artistic and methodological means of the work owner. Therefore, a compound sentence, which is the object of our research in the text, can be given as a simple sentence or as a few simple sentences used separately..

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